

Global mining cryptocurrency backed by Real Estate investments

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

With the rapid growth of the crypto currencies, it's getting hard to focus on which one to invest, as the fluctuation is really abrasive. Safe trading of crypto currency is not an option as no one has ever been able to minimize the risk. AARNAV is one of the first cryptocurrency that offers a unique mechanism called safety net effect.

The safety net is a very smart and appropriate way of tackling the major issue of RISK in a volatile crypto world. Presuming that the crypto currency market crashes and the value of bitcoin drops to \$1000, AARNAV will not be affected, as its backbone will be the real estate market, which will increase, as investors will be moving from the crypto market to the real estate market. This is the crash proof plan that eradicates a large percentage of risk from investments.

Though, there are quite a few cryptos which are dedicated for specific purposes, AARNAV is one of the first currency through which international real estate properties can be bought. AARNAV will be offering real estate properties for New York, California, Auckland, Melbourne, Sydney, Delhi and Dubai. AARNAV will concentrate on these regions together with our trusted team of professionals and will concrete AARNAV's portfolio of investments via adding

2. Aim

ARM's vision is a token that is based on crypto mining backed by real estate investments for secure and steady returns. We as a team are focused to plough in mining farms throughout USA, the reason being cost effective electricity. In the meanwhile, investments in real estate throughout hot markets in world will secure and backup our portfolio token holders.

3. Material and methods

We are using ASIC miners predominantly

1. Bitman antminer S9—13T, 14T (Bitcoin mining)

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2. Bitman antminer L3+ (litecoin mining)
3. Ethereum E3 (Ethereum mining, latest one)

We will be installing these equipment's in our mining facilities

1. New York (Niagara Falls Region)
2. Washington (Chelan region)

We will be using hydroelectric power, as it is cheaper (approximately .06c/ Kw, which is the cheapest in the world). Hence proven profitable for our operations.

4. Results

Principal investments of investors will be secured within the first year of operation. This one of a kind Hybrid investment token is a crowd-funded approach that has a back-up crash proof plan. Arm token holders will benefit in many ways. They will be able to benefit from the boom in hot real estate markets and crypto mining. This will allow token holders to ensure security to principal amount of token purchased and at the same high return, as long as they hold the token.

5. Conclusions

If a conclusion has to be made for the existing scenario, the real estate developers and other finance related institutions would exhibit undivided attention to invest in crypto mining and real estate business. This immense attention and support from the real estate investors induces the spirit in team AARNAV to take it step ahead. On speaking with respect to ARM's future plans, all trades made, the assets acquired, sold, held, or transferred such as real estate, investments and mining farms will be integrated with the ARM blockchain.

6. Keywords

Blockchain, mining, software wallet, hardware wallet, cold storage, sharding, fork, node, mining rig, safety net, hybrid token

Author biography

Gurpreet Kaur My name is Gurpreet Kaur. I have my bachelors in Biology from the State University of New York. I have created ARM token on ERC20 ethereum network. Being a cryptographer, I have learnt how to mine the best algorithms, by switching between the best mining pools for better payouts. I have been a cryptocurrency miner since 2016, dealing with equipment's that included Antminer S9, Nvidia 1070 Yi, Nvidia 1080, Nvidia 1080ti and most recently Antminer L3+. I am proud to be leading and working with a team of professionals that have tremendous experience in their given fields. Together, we will create a niche that will be growth focused. Being the CEO of AARNAV token, I have a commitment for transparency, honesty, and credibility to our token holders.

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